

Prime determinants that influence “Life Expectancy”: an analysis across Indian states using multiple regressions

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Abstract

Background/Objectives: To explore life expectancy in Indian states and also to determine how life expectancy is influenced by determinants such as gender, per-capita income, gender, age and area.

Method/ Statistical Analysis: An extensive literature review from various developing and developed countries was initially done to understand the validity of indicators. Suitable indicators that can be focused for Indian states were selected. Secondary data from reliable sources and databases (For Ex. Like India Stat) were collected to perform this study. Regression analysis applying linear multiple regression and stepwise regression using Minitab software has been extensively used to arrive at the key determinants that affect life expectancy in various Indian states.

Findings: Overall, the analyses of the Indian states indicate that literacy rate, access of doctors in rural areas, income, preferences of states (inclusive of geography) by Indian people to reside play as key factors in determining and improving Life Expectancy. Findings include that females have a higher life expectancy than males living in the urban area in most of the Indian states. Also, findings indicate that literacy rate and net income plays a significant role in affecting life expectancy at birth positively in both urban and rural areas in all the states. Geography of the states also plays a key factor that affects life expectancy. Findings indicate that people who live in mid and south India have a higher life expectancy than those residing in the northern states.

Improvement/ Applications: Findings and analysis indicates the suitable steps, that the policy makers of state as well as centre need to take, that can enhance life expectancy and quality of life across the Indian states. Also certain other factors like type of diseases that inhibit life expectancy can be studied in future in detail as they may influence life expectancy in a higher way.

Keywords: Life expectancy, Quality of life, Policy, Indian states, Regression modelling.

1. Introduction

In this paper, we try to explore and understand certain factors that are statistically significant and which influence as well as determine “life expectancy” using multiple regression analysis across Indian states. From the results obtained through regression, we can prioritize major factors in health as well as in economy that are at risk for well-being of an individual as well as aid central as well as state level policy makers to strategize public policies.

1.1 Background

Life Expectancy reflects the quality of life in a particular place, which may be a specific area of a city, or a city itself, or a state or a country, though it may only be a qualitative reflection. Further the well-being of an individual is determined by this term “Life Expectancy” as he/she hopes to live holistically fuller and longer lives. Life expectancy estimates a person’s life span which is derived by averaging the age of entire population who die in a particular year. More about the life expectancy parameters are provided in the subsection of data definition in Section 3 of this paper.

One of the parameters of life expectancy i.e. life expectancy at birth, which is an indicator that has been used across the globe has shown an increase in many nations across the globe, though across some developing nations like Sub-Saharan Africa in particular, it has been decreasing. Thus, life expectancy is one of the key

factors that also indicate Human development of a country and also describes the physical quality of life of a specific area.

Further several empirical studies indicate that certain factors like caste, gender, income, diseases that causes mortality like heart diseases, cancer, and certain factors of risk for premature death have influenced life expectancy parameters. In this study, we focus on statistical health economic factors like availability of hospitals/physicians/doctors, apart from few other mentioned factors above, in context of Indian states to come with and provide health policy implications.

1.2 Research question

In this paper, we focus and try to find answer to how factors like literacy and availability of public health support i.e. number of physicians available in rural or urban areas of Indian states that affect "Life Expectancy" apart from trying to whether certain other influential factors like age-group, gender and area affect "Life Expectancy" across Indian states in the period of 2010-14.

1.3 A study of relevant literature

Articles in this section which reviews the literature, provides valid indicators of life expectancy in developing as well as developed countries that have been obtained using multiple regression. The effect of life expectancy and its relationship with economic growth with articles focused on Indian states is also portrayed. A few articles show how the various variables that affect life expectancy in various contexts inclusive of geography trends and well-being of an individual. In [1] uses Gini coefficients obtained by running regressions for life expectancy that are calculated across the fifty states of USA, and separately for men and women. Through this innovative technique for assessing life expectancy, the authors obtain certain important findings like increase of female life expectancy across states increase with poverty rate, pollution and percentage white. The results were also applicable for males.

In [2] explores the life expectancy parameters effect on economic growth. Their study tries to estimate life expectancy's effect on a wide variety of economy variables inclusive of population as well as GDP. The results of this paper indicate that population increases with increase in life expectancy and so was the GDP, but it does not compensate or adapt to the population's increase. Further with life expectancy's increase, income per capita decreases. Further the authors indicate that, with lack of evidence that income per capita will grow due to life expectancy increase. A certain amount of caution has been advised by the authors with reference to the results as diseases in the current era may have a different impact than the diseases which occurred 40-50 years back.

In [3] explore the relationship between life expectancy and quality of life which was expressed by nutritional, economic and environmental measures. A multivariate analysis was done to arrive at the results. Further linear regression models were developed to relate life expectancy to variables like literacy rate, health expenditures on a per capita basis and drinking water access. The linear regression yielded a correlation of 0.88. In [4] studied the effect of gender as well as education for different ethnic groups and races in USA in 1970, 1980 and 1990. The findings were that at lower levels of education, significant racial differences exist in the expectancy.

In [5] conducted an empirical study of developed countries specifically the OECD countries using OLS regression. Their study indicates that consumption of pharmaceutical items increases the life expectancy especially in mid and advanced ages. The study also indicates that lifestyle factors like alcohol consumption, tobacco consumption, fruits, vegetables, butter also affect life expectancy rates. In [6] describe the importance of "Healthy life expectancy" and its indices that are affected by change of population's mental and physical health. Further it considers on how the success of political program is correlated with these measures. In [7] describes that community health centre, poverty and smoking have relatively higher statistical significant effect on life expectancy while other factors like obesity, un-insurance, race, exercise etc. are less significant.

In [8] evaluates the performance on human development which is related to life expectancy of fifteen major Indian states in the period of 1981-2001. The empirical study was done using the OLS study. The results indicate that there has been a convergence in parameters of well-being though there is a slight divergence of per capita income across states. A study of states falling into virtuous as well as vicious cycles was done by the authors who led to findings that six of the states falling in virtuous cycle whereas as many as eight states fell in the vicious cycle category. These results meant that certain policies can be sequence in such a way that Human development is strengthened which may lead to formation of a virtuous cycle. Further resource allocation needs

to be evenly distributed across education, health drinking water and sanitation which will lead states in vicious category to move towards the virtuous category which finally leads to economic growth.

Major developed countries and developing countries participated in an analysis [9] in his study uses multiple regression as well as probity frameworks were to determine the effect of socio-economic factors for around 90 plus developing countries. The study which classified the countries into three groups based on life expectancy indicated that many socio-economic factors like education, urbanization, per-capita income were not that relevant in determination of life expectancy in developing countries. The analyses by the authors also suggest that policies and programs relating to adult illiteracy improvement, physician's availability needs to be formulated to improve the life expectancy.

In [10] which were done using the principles of multiple regressions. Stepwise regression which is a type of multiple regression was also used as this is a sounder technique. Based on the regression results, it was found that life expectancy increases with increase in population growth, safe water access, fertility and decreases with increase in diseases like AIDS, tuberculosis, deforestation rate etc. Also, the studies by authors indicated that geography plays a significant role in life expectancy as found out in case of life expectancy of Africa which was lower than its comparable continent Asia. This finding definitely underscores the effect of sanitation, illness and economic factors which are meaningful and the organizations need to assist these developing regions for overcoming these critical issues.

In [11] in their research paper yielded contradictory results between well-being of an individual and the life expectancy of an individual as the results of the model developed showed the trend that with decreasing life expectancy, well-being increased. This also meant that other than physical health, many other human aspects contribute to well-being. Also, the studies reveal that life expectancy may not be an appropriate variable to measure population health, but can be useful in measuring quality of life.

In [12] paper's study reveals that health which was measured through life expectancy and distribution of income are relative and has no links with absolute income which leads to the importance of measuring relative poverty. Further as this research was done in a developed country, research implied that if differences in health was a function of inequality of income, then differences that arise in health due to social class differences, have never decreases despite poverty falling to lower levels.

2. Data

Table 1. Definition of dependent variable used in study

Dependent Variable	Definition	Data source	Year
Life Expectancy	Denotes the actual expectation of life at an age x viz. The mean number of years in future, a person will live if the current trends of mortality continued	India Stat& Office of Registrar General and Census Commissioner, India	2010-14

2.1. Data source

The data that has been utilized in the study of this paper comes from one of the most comprehensive database with reference to socio-economic statistical data known as India Stat, which contain India specific data of 56 clustered sites.

These data are also state specific, region specific and sector specific and provides the academic, corporate research fraternity with authentic and comprehensive compilation of socio-economic secondary statistical data about India and its states. The variables considered in this study have been defined in Section 2.2 in Table 1 and 2 for reader's convenience.

Table 2. Definition of key independent Variables used in study

Independent Variable	Definition	Data source	Year
Literacy Rate	The total percentage of the population of a state at a particular year of time when the person is aged seven years or above who can read and write with understanding. The denominator denotes the overall population aged seven years or more. (Due to data constraints, we have taken five or more years*)	India Stat& Office of Registrar General and Census Commissioner, India	2010-14
Per capita Income	Per capita or average income measures the mean income earned per person in a given region (here we have taken state) in a specified year. The calculation is done by dividing the area's total income by its total population.	Same as Above	2014
Primary Health Care Doctors	Primary Health Centre (PHCs), also referred to as public health centres, is a state's rural health care facilities. The doctors available in these basic units are known as PHC doctors	Same as Above	2014
Sex/Gender	Being female or male	Same as Above	2010-14
Age - Group	Number of people classified in the same age	Same as Above	2010-14
Area	Urban or Rural based on population density	Same as Above	2010-14
State	Local authorities within the territory of India based on linguism, culture etc. (20 States are considered for study**)	Same as Above	2010-14

2.2. Data definition

The author has considered five years or more as an approximation rather than seven years or more due to data availability in five-year ranges.

Data was available only for twenty states at the time of 2010-2014. The next data will be available in 2018 for period 2014-18 for additional states.

3. Methodology, analyses and results

The data obtained from the data source mentioned in the previous section were visually inspected for any missing entries. After verification, the data were formatted in Microsoft Excel according to the needs of the statistical software. Minitab version 17.0 is statistical software used in this study for regression modelling and statistical analyses. As most of the models developed in the given study had qualitative variables with more than one category, they were created and coded as indicator variables (for representing dummies) in Minitab.

3.1 Assumptions for development of regression models

- 1) One of the most important assumptions was that the relationship between quantitative independent variables and Life Expectancy were linear and subjected to randomness.
- 2) We would have liked to collect data for all twenty-nine states, but could gather the secondary data for only twenty states as some of the states, primarily the north-eastern states and newly formed states like Telangana, Goa etc. did not release the statistics of the required variables. The study assumes that the twenty states represent a good reflection of Indian population in overall aspects.
- 3) Due to inconsistencies in availability of data, some of the data collected like per capita income, literacy rate, number of doctors available in primary health centres were collected in the given period of 2010-2014 at a

certain point say 2014. It is assumed that not much fluctuations in social as well as economic conditions occurred in the given period and thus the data set for these variables is appropriate.

3.2 Initial regression models and analysis

Initial model was generated by regressing the dependent variable “Life Expectancy” with independent variables like geography which is represented by the states (20 states), age –group (19 age groups) and per capita income. During the regression process, the variable “per capita income” came out with a Variation Inflation factor of 29 which implied that there may be a multi co linearity issue between categorical variables and per capita income. This is because per capita income has a high correlation with age-group and the states of the country. This meant that many of states as well as age-groups affected the per capita income which appeared valid at the point of time. Hence this was removed and the regression was re-run with the categorical variables. The regression results are shown in Appendix A. The residual plots are also shown in Appendix A with residuals following a normal distributed histogram and almost constantly hovering around zero symmetrically. This indicated that model is highly valid, though the relationship between Life Expectancy and Age-Group may be attributed to endogeneity between them and which is also shown by the extra-ordinarily high value of R square value below in the model summary.

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq (adj)	R-sq (pred)
0.694307	99.91%	99.90%	99.89%

The model obtained next was regressing life expectancy with age group and gender. This again gave results similar to the above one and is represented in Appendix B. Where-as the previous model had “states” as the independent variable along with age group, this model had gender along with age-group. A regression done individually with reference to these two variables indicated that while gender did show some percentage contribution as it was statistically significant (p <0.05) as well as medium R square value, states did not have any statistical significance(p>0.05) as well as had zero R square value when regressed independently to Life Expectancy.

3.3. The importance of r-square value and p-value in regression models

R-square explains variation in the model. So, 0.1 R-square means 10% of variation is explained within the data. The greater R-square value, the more the model would be better. P-value tells about the F statistic hypothesis testing. So, if the p-value is less than the significance level (usually 0.05 for 95% confidence level), the more statistically significance the variable which can be seen from its co-efficient. Thus, there are four scenarios: Low R-square and low p-value (p-value <= 0.05), Low R-square and high p-value (p-value > 0.05) High R-square and low p-value, High R-square and high p-value.

Interpretation of the above situations are It means that model explains a lot of variation within the data and is significant, It means that model explains a lot of variation within the data but is not significant, In the forthcoming models, we have looked at situation 3 where the model explains a lot of variation within the data and is significant. (Typically taken R-square value to be more than 60% and p value to be around 0.05). Further going on, Life expectancy otherwise stated would be treated as Life expectancy at Birth, It means that model doesn't explain variation of the data but it is significant, it means that model doesn't explain variation of the data and it is not significant.

3.4 Regression models containing statistically significant control and independent variables like doctors available in rural areas, net – income, literacy rate and gender

The next model in Appendix C shows that Life Expectancy at birth is correlated highly when regressed with gender and most of the States when the population is considered from the urban area. This model’s findings include that females have a higher life expectancy than males living in the urban area. A few states that can be omitted for these observations are Tamil Nadu, Gujarat etc. which are not statistically significant due to high p-Values. One of the probable reasons that could be attributed to this observation, is that women belonging to urban areas are more health conscious than women at rural health areas where people tend not to go to

doctors or regular health check-up or even beauty conscious, due to reasons of expenses that may occur and which the urban females would be able to spend.

The model in Appendix D again provides the anticipated relation that in rural areas Life Expectancy is well correlated with Literacy rate which is statistically significant whereas the availability of doctors does not impact life expectancy. This is possible because probably because of pollution free environment and a presence of health green environment in villages. It is probably due these reasons, along with expenses for doctor which prohibits people to go to health centres. Thus, the availability of doctors may be a dormant factor in providing better life expectancy to rural population.

Finally, the regression model in Appendix E provides information that both literacy rate and net income plays a significant role in affecting life expectancy at birth positively in both urban and rural areas. This is well expected because education along with a good salary should improve the quality of life and hence life expectancy. Though the R-square value is medium valued, this model is worth looking at.

3.5 Exploring Life Expectancy at Birth(0-4years), Mid-age (45-50 years), Old age (85+ years) through multiple regression

There are some interesting findings regarding Life Expectancy in Mid-age (45-50 years) as shown in Appendix F. Mid age people, specifically female from Urban areas in states like J&K, Kerala, Punjab, Rajasthan, Uttarakhand, Himachal Pradesh and Bihar tend to live longer as these variables are statistically significant and the life expectancy is positively correlated whereas Chhattisgarh state people live shorter by 3years. This can be attributed to many facts and study can be done in urban areas of these states and can be replicated across other states for other persons, specifically female to enjoy these benefits.

Appendix G shows the findings of life expectancy in old age (85+) years where conducive conditions are existent in states like Haryana, AP, HP, Punjab, Rajasthan, J&K, and Uttarakhand. Further female live longer in these states. It is also seen that Life expectancy depends and is positively correlated with literacy rates.

This regression results are obtained by stepwise regression which is a special type of multiple regression and brings out those variables which are statistically significant without high variance inflation factors. We see that most of the variance inflation factors over around 1.5-2.00 which shows the absence of multi co linearity.

The Final regression which is also stepwise regression shows that life expectancy at birth is dependent on states like Jharkhand, J&K, HP, Bihar and correlated positively whereas in other states like Tamil Nadu, Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Haryana, Gujarat, Chhattisgarh the life expectancy goes down. All these states are statistically significant variables.

Further Rural areas also show lower expectancy than urban areas. As per earlier findings, female live longer and life expectancy increases with literacy rate and per-capita income. Further the summary in all the three appendix shows that R-square value is medium (60 %+) to high (80% and above) in all the three cases which makes these models worthy to consider more detail from many other aspects.

4. Conclusions

As life expectancy is a key indicator for health in both developing as well as developed countries, promotion of opportunities for increasing life expectancy must be focussed by policy makers.

In this study, we have generated data where we have seen life expectancy as function of states (inclusive of geography of states), gender, income, literacy rate, doctors in rural areas and finally whether people stay in urban or rural areas.

Policy makers both at centre and state level may take this study as a start point to develop strategies for improving Public health. They may consider the following possibilities that have come through the findings.

- 1) Replicate the best practices mainly in urban areas of the states where the life expectancy has been found higher.
- 2) Educate and make people literate about health as it has been found a very important factor throughout the study
- 3) Sketch a proper strategy for access to doctors at PHCs in rural areas.

Finally, The analyses of these twenty Indian states indicates that literacy rate, access of doctors in rural areas, income, preferences of states (inclusive of geography) play as key factors in determining and improving

Life Expectancy. Certain other factors like smoker study, certain type of diseases that inhibit life expectancy can be studied in future in detail as they may influence life expectancy in a higher way.

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